

THE GROUP WORKS IN THE CLASSROOM FOR ENGAGEMENT IN CREATIVE WRITING OF SHS GRADE 12 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Groupwork activities are one of the teacher's methods of teaching so that the students engage in the lessons and participate in the interests of each student. Groupwork activities help students improve their 21st-century skills such as communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking. One of the common problems of senior high school teachers is the students engage and connect with socialization in the classroom. This study highlights the importance of group work activities in constructivism theory. The research was conducted in a public school in Antipolo City with participants of 109 Grade 12 SHS from GAS, HUMSS, and OSH. The study utilized quantitative research with the use of a survey questionnaire. To analyze the data, researchers used descriptive analysis by analyzing the students' perceptions of group work activity in the classroom. The study found that students preferred group activities such as discussion, reporting, and role-playing during the class lesson. The students chose group work activities of engagement, participation in the classroom, and developing communication. However, the majority of students believed that group work activities lead to relying in the classroom on their classmates while creating conflict and collusion in the group. The researcher suggests that the teachers, school staff, and school administrators design group work activities. The classroom has an environment of fun and enjoyment so that students participate in the lesson. The school administration discussed the implementation of group work activities in the classroom so that students will be involved in the classroom. The school will conduct extended research on learning development by conducting group work activities.

Keywords: *Constructivism, Metacognition, Andragogy, Groupwork, Socio-cultural learning*

INTRODUCTION

Group work activities improve 21st-century skills in communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking in creative writing subject. Although creative writing needs constant hands-on monitoring by the teacher, it can still also be conducted in group work activities, which can develop the collaborative exchange of ideas. Undoubtedly, adolescent learners are interested in games to practice ideas and knowledge (Rahimi & Kim, 2018; Seric, 2018; Orme et al., 2020; Qarabash et al., 2019) while having to interact with teachers and classmates (Nipp & Palenque, 2017; Gillies, 2006). However, creative writing subject is an almost individual activity in the classroom, which can possibly be monotonous learning that leads to the disinterest of the students in the classroom. It can cause students' disengagement in socialization and potential non-performance students in class, especially in a public school scenario. It can possibly solve the problems of lacking interest and disengagement in the classroom setting, which can also involve different learning aspects. The creative writing activities develop cognitive abilities and affective skills in socialization in the giving activities (Ainsworth, 2021). The mental abilities of the learner manage the step-by-step process by using critical thinking to solve the problem, while affection skills practice socialization in managing various emotions, even having activities with tensions as well as this activity will avoid monotonous learning environments while the teacher conducts lessons. The students build ideas and thoughts that create the big picture of the knowledge scheme and structured lesson.

The recent result of PISA (2018) found that Philippine numeracy and literacy got the lowest rank among Asian countries, which can be alarming in the Philippine educational system. It could be possible that the education delivery of the teacher has the great factor of having low literacy in the Philippines, in which the majority of the classrooms are oversized in number. So, the group work activities in writing, as student-centred education, should be implemented with a clear plan, implementation, and evaluation, which build camaraderie and self-directed learning. Therefore, writing with a group improves the student's knowledge construction in the classroom through the help and support of their classmates. Socialization molds the students in communication and participation with groupmates with various ideas and thoughts in the classroom. Therefore, learner diversity is the best practice for the senior high school to practice skills that will be used for future academic and professional work.

Learning in socialization

Group work produces students' collaboration and positive effects on grade improvement, cognitive and emotional. Group work activities produce collaboration and positive effects on both cognitive and emotional aspects of senior high school students, improving grades and academic performance in the class (Ainsworth, 2021). Moreover, based on the study of Hung & Long (2019) and Vizconde (2022), the students develop language skills in socialization by practicing interaction in given activities which, produced

positive effects, especially in English for Foreign Language (EFL). Through student collaboration, group work produces positive effects on grade improvement and cognitive and emotional in language and literature. The students experience positive effects in the exchanging of ideas and insight regarding the lessons. Exchanging ideas with classmates strengthens and increases the knowledge in the lesson. Grouping can be hard to manage because of the tension created in the atmosphere due to the various cultures, ideas, and thoughts in the classroom that sometimes create tension in the classroom (Mittelmeier et al., 2018; Seric, 2018). Still, this is a good preparatory for the learners for socialization in real life in which they can able to adapt to the diversity of people inside and outside the school. Group work lets the students experience the real event in their surroundings as part of socialization. During group work, socialization improves as well as the language skills of the students in the classroom through communication. The students discussed with other groups step-by-step procedures based on the outcomes of the learners, which built metacognition during the class. The students develop self-regulatory in groupings by evaluating their learning styles. According to Ulla (2021), students increase learning attention and focus in the study, which helps them to be more interested in the lessons. Despite the benefits of learning

Self-directed learning

Through group work activities, students engage in autonomous learning areas alone in which they manage their learning process (Grau et al., 2018). Through the self-directed learning process in group activities, the students take the initiative based on the assigned roles of the members. The students act accordingly because the responsibility for the program or outcome of the activities will depend on their participation. The group activity creates interactive communication in which students share ideas, feelings, and knowledge about the topic or lesson. Hence, students lead to self-reflection based on the activities that used various learning skills in learning socialization. Grouping activities are the representation of the real world in the professional field as the practice for work. Identifying the learning process is an essential student skill for study and work that answers to the complexities of subjects daily. Additionally, students themselves solve various critical problems through socialization the same time utilizing a self-reflective approach. As per the study by Qarabash et al. (2019), the teacher used technology such as video with their groupmates to record the activity. Therefore, the students have an opportunity to reflect on their own work for the improvement of future activities. Self-reflective helps the students to understand the outcomes by correcting their own work errors in a certain activity to become the foundation of the learning as well and the students enjoy the class activities to improve learning.

Based on Williams et al. (2019), high-achieving learners work with groupmates to finish the tasks in the classroom. Despite of positive effects of groupings, Grzmek et al. (2020) found that some students do not participate due to their past experiences in a group activity. The students experienced unfair evaluation, which is the equal

dissemination of the activities done by a few members only (Seric, 2018), in which sometimes the conducting of group work creates tension in various cultural backgrounds (Mittlemeier, 2018), and even the teachers are hesitance to conduct group activities in the classroom because extra efforts to prepare (Chiriac et al., 2011). This study looked for the advantages and disadvantages of group work in creative writing in senior high school. This study helps the teachers prepare for the preparation in conducting group activities in the classroom.

Positive and negative effects of group work activities

Collaboration is one of the essential skills for building knowledge with fellow classmates. Building knowledge includes positive effects on the learners in the lesson. Delaney et al. (2019) stated that there is a positive relationship between board participation and learning performance tasks. Although some studies showed that high-achieving students work alone, however, Williams et al. (2019) argued that students improve learning by enjoying group work in which they have a companion who supports their emotions and interests in the activities. Moreover, disagreement in the grouping has great advantages to the learning of the students; at the same time, students can able to minimize the workloads of the activities. Based on the results showed that group work has had positive effects on the student's grades, learning, and critical development skills in the learners from their past, either positive or negative (Grzimek et al., 2020). Based on the study of Omar (2022), the majority of the students agreed that cooperative group works as a flexible learning strategy during a pandemic. Additionally, group work activities improve socialization and metacognition in learning (De Vera & Marasigan, 2020; Grau et al., 2018). According to Hung (2019), the students got positive effects in grouping in improving language communication in English as a Foreign Language. It showed that the group activities develop the communication skills of senior high school and even ESL learners. Ulla (2021) discovered that the majority of the students increase the students' attention in the lesson using group work activities, which is part of engagement in communication skills.

On the contrary, there are possible negative effects of conducting group work activities, such as tension, online distance challenges, and hindrances to conducting group work. Belgica et al. (2020) and Fabian et al. (2021) found there are other negative effects of grouping, such as group work discomfort, problems with an internet connection, unstable internet, lack of communication, and lack of cooperation. Moreover, Chiriac et al. (2011) mentioned that factors are not only students but teachers' reluctance to do group work activities in the classroom due to the learning process and learning outcomes. The teacher is reluctant to conduct group work in the leadership and teachership of the teachers. The difficulties in handling classroom group work can possibly result found by Mittelmeier et al. (2018), students experienced tension in group work in cross-cultural diversity. Social relationships are essential for the learning of the students in the

classroom. As well as Seric (2018) also discovered that group work activities identify the risks and benefits of group work in terms of gender and national aspects in the classroom.

Theoretical Framework and Conceptual Framework

Metacognition, Constructivism, Socio-cultural learning, Andragogy

According to (Bodner, 1986), learners construct a body of knowledge with the help of their fellow classmates, which has a positive effect on the learning of the students. Therefore, **constructivism** designs activities that involve the participation of the learners in every activity. Additionally, through engaging in activities in the classroom, each student develops their emotional, physical, and socialization in the various behaviors.

The socio-cultural, according to Vygotsky (1978), learners develop socialization as part of the learning level for collaboration and participation in the class. Through socialization, students improve their conversation abilities, problem-solving, and affection aspects with their classmates. As the Senior High school level is considered near adult learning, therefore the students have the capacity to learn independently and manage their own learning by discovery with the groups. Based on the book of (writer proponents, year) andragogy level of education, the learners find the answer in the knowledge questions based upon the problems of their surroundings.

In the constructivism theory (Fernando, 2017), the students learn by building knowledge by brainstorming with their classmates. The students improve learning through socialization with their classmates at school in the activities in the grouping. Group work activities practice various skills in communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking skills in 21st-century learning. The students have the ability to adapt to their environment in solving the problems and struggles in individual and community. Through the activities in the lesson, the students improve.

Piaget & Inhelder (2000) believed that the cognitive development of learners is not only the learning knowledge but also the construction of the knowledge from their childhood. From the very beginning of the student's growth, the student started to develop his cognitive development, which has four stages such as sensorimotor (birth to 2 years), preoperational (2 to 7 years), concrete operational (7 to 11 years), and formal operational (ages 12 and up). It indicated that the learning of the students is formed by constructing the learning, which included the grouping activities that not only the individual works but also the socialization in the classroom form.

According to the theory of Vygotsky (1978), also known as sociocultural, cognitive development, the students' environment has a great impact on the development of their knowledge. The student's environment as part of the group activities and students'

socialization in the classroom. The intellectual and social setting of the students can also mould the classroom in practicing the skills.

" The most significant moment in the course of intellectual development, which gives birth to the purely human forms of practical and abstract intelligence, occurs when speech and practical activity, two previously completely independent lines of development, converge." - Vygotsky, 1978

It showed in the quotation that students learned through socialization by converging with the knowledge that moulds the ability to communicate with others. As John Dewey (1916) mentioned the environment sustains the continuous self-renewal of educational growth in the classroom by nurturing, including group activities by fostering, cultivating, and processing. He believed that the students need to interact with their fellow classmates at school and learn by doing. Students learned with the development in handwork with their classmates. Through the various ideas of their fellow classmates, new knowledge emerged, which develops both their emotional and cognitive abilities in the study, which leads to engagement in the classroom.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Perception of groupwork activities of SHS students

The framework showed that the student's perceptions in terms of self-regulatory activities resulted in more studies in conducting the lessons in the classroom. The self-regulatory activities develop the student in how to learn through their self-regulation in the classroom. Students who answered are the perceptions using self-regulatory activities

such as note-taking, portfolio, assignment, activity/ quizzes, journaling, problem-solving activities, and community-based learning in terms of positive and negative effects the SHS students in public school. The results of the data will be the guide for the recommendation and action plans of the school for designing the implementation of self-regulatory activities.

Figure 1 showed that the student's perception of group work activities in the classroom. The group work activities affect the development of their study. The students will answer the following preferred learning such: reporting, assignment, video making/ blogging, discussion, role play, portfolio, card games, and problem-solving. The students' perceptions are the development of the learning. The students will answer based on their perception of the advantages of group work activities given by the teacher and the disadvantages of the given activities.

Research Questions

1. What are the demographical profiles of respondents in terms of;
 - a. gender
 - b. age
 - c. strand
2. What types of group work are preferred by senior high students?
3. What is the group work satisfaction of senior high students in the classroom?
4. What are the disadvantages of group work for senior high school students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Location

This study is a descriptive analysis that utilized a self-made single survey questionnaire. The data was gathered within November 2022 using an online questionnaire for senior high school students. This study was conducted in a public school in Antipolo City, which had the second-largest population in the city of junior and senior high school students. This school was near the commercial area in which the majority of the students came from a different region.

Respondents and Sampling Procedures

The total number of students is 243 from GAS, HUMSS, and OHS senior high school students distributed in a public school in Antipolo city. The researcher considered the 5% marginal errors of the total number of participants in specific strands. Therefore, the researcher used sloven's formula to get the expected number of participants. It was found that at least 109 students at senior high school participated.

Research Instrument

The research utilized 5 points Likert scale (1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Very Agree) to get the perception of senior high school students in terms of research-based learning in self-directed learning, project-based learning, community-based learning, problem-based learning, and last the disadvantages of research-based learning.

Content Validity and Reliability

The research questionnaire was validated by the two members of the senior high school faculty in research, social studies, and business management as an expert in their field for validation of survey content.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the approval of the principal to conduct research, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to the selected strands of senior high school students in the intended location. Before the distribution, the researcher gives the instructions and asks permission from the participants.

Ethical Consideration

Before conducting the survey, the researcher asked the principal's permission to conduct a study on senior high school students. The participants were well informed about the nature and confidentiality of their personal data input in the survey questionnaire. Each student was not forced to answer the survey form.

Statistical Tools and Analysis

The research worked with descriptive statistics to calculate the variables in the research. The research counted the frequency distribution and percentage and ranked the data. Moreover, the second part of the research survey counted the weighted mean, standard derivation, and the total average weighted mean to interpret the data while using verbal interpretation.

Scale	Range	Response	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral	Moderately High
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographical profile of the respondents

Table 1: Demographical Profile

Demographical Profile	Total		Rank
	<i>f</i>	%	
Sex			
Male	44	40%	2
Female	65	60%	1
Total	109	100.0%	
Age			
16-17	40	37%	2
18-19	54	50%	1
20-21	10	9%	3
22 and above	5	5%	4
Total	109	100.0%	
Strands			
GAS A 12	16	15%	3
GAS B 12	11	10%	4
GAS C 12	11	10%	4
HUMSS C 12	30	28%	2
HUMSS D 12	34	31%	1
OHS 12	7	6%	6
Total	109	100.0%	

Table 1 above shows the demographical profile of the respondent in terms of sex, age, and strands/ grades from senior high school in the year 2022-2023. The data found that the majority of the participants were females, with 77 (77%), followed by males with 46(46%). It showed that female students participated most in the survey.

While most of the students who participated were in the age of 18-19 years old, with a total number of 51 (60%), followed by 16-17 years old, with age 44 (36%). Additionally, the lowest part, 20 and above ages, got 18 (15%). It implied that the senior high school students are still in the proper age range of senior high school level due to the proper total number of expected ages from senior high school.

The HUMSS C strands got the highest number of participants in the survey, with 35 (29%), and HUMSS D had 30 (24%). At the same time, the OHS (open high school) got the lowest number of participants, with 9 (7%). It implied that the number of participants depends upon the number of respondents.

Table 2: Preferred activities of senior high school students in self-regulatory

Items	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranks	Verbal Interpretation
a. Reporting	1	3	20	52	33	4.04	2.01	2	High
b. Assignments	3	7	31	44	24	3.72	1.93	5	High
c. Video Making/ blogging	4	12	37	38	18	3.10	1.76	8	Moderately High
d. Discussion	1	2	17	35	54	4.28	2.07	1	Very High
e. Role Play	3	4	29	39	34	3.89	1.97	3	High
f. Portfolio	4	7	42	29	27	3.62	1.90	6	High
g. Card games	3	7	21	48	30	3.87	1.97	4	High
h. Problem-solving	1	13	45	37	13	3.44	1.85	7	High
Average Weighted Mean						4.28	2.21		Very High

Table 2 shows the preferred activities of senior high school students in self-regulatory activities at school. The majority of the learners showed preferred discussion in the class, which improves the student's ability to share and collaborate with their classmates at school, which got a weighted mean of 4.28 (*Very High*). Carrasco & Torres Iribara (2018) found that most of the students develop self-expression in political, social, and also gender-equal rights in the classroom. Then, followed by reporting, students selected reporting as the group work activity at school had 4.04 (*High*). Chiriac (2014) mentioned that group work activities, including reporting, serve as successful pedagogy as well as an incentive to the learners because they express themselves in class. Next, most students chose role-playing as one of their preferred group work activities in the

class. According to Chesler & Fox (1996) said, role-playing becomes the pathway of interaction in the classroom at the same time, developing the interpersonal ability of the learners. Moreover, the students' leaders pretend to be the characters in acting, students examine the issues of the story, and students can able to experience the real world of imagination.

Table 3: Senior high school students in research-based learning in 21st-century skills

Items	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1. Group work activities help me to learn faster.	1	5	13	38	52	4.24	2.06	3	Very High
2. Group work activities make the task easier.	2	5	13	39	50	4.19	2.05	6	High
3. Group work activities improve engagement in the classroom.	1	2	15	34	57	4.32	2.08	1	Very High
4. Group work activities enhance my communication with classmates.	1	3	13	36	56	4.31	2.08	2	Very High
5. Group work activities encourage me to participate in class.	2	3	17	36	51	4.20	2.05	5	High
6. Group work activities construct knowledge with my students.	1	2	19	41	46	4.18	2.05	7	High
7. Group work activities are more enjoyable	7	6	14	31	51	4.04	2.01	9	High

than individual groups.									
8. Group work activities develop my skills in creative writing.	1	2	17	42	47	4.21	2.05	4	Very High
9. Group work activities create lifelong learning.	1	3	25	41	39	4.05	2.01	8	High
10. Group work activities develop my emotions and thoughts.	1	6	22	41	39	4.02	2.00	10	High
Average Weighted Mean						4.18	2.04		High

Table 3 showed that senior high school students chose group work activities to improve them for in the engagement in the classroom. Engaging in the classroom improves the students to become active learning in the classroom. The students practice various skills needed for 21st-century learning skills. As Ulla (2021) discovered, the majority of the students increase the students' attention in the lesson using group work activities, which is part of engagement in communication skills.

Additionally, the students selected group work to enhance their communication with their fellow classmates. Communication is one of the essential skills of students for the future level in the tertiary and professional fields. According to Hung (2019), the students got positive effects in grouping in improving language communication in English as a Foreign Language.

And then, for senior high school students, the group work activities help them to learn faster. It implies that students learn faster if there have the help of their classmates. According to (Bodner, 1986), students construct their knowledge to create positive effects to the learner of the students as engagement in physical, emotional, and social behavior.

Table 4: The disadvantages of group work activities of senior high school students

Items	S D (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	S A (5)	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1. Group work activities are unfair evaluations in the classroom.	8	18	49	22	12	3.11	1.76	4	Moderately High
2. Group work activities are unbalance learning tasks for each member.	10	20	43	21	15	2.75	1.66	8	Moderately High
3. Group work activities lead some students to rely upon their classmates' efforts.	5	9	33	35	27	3.64	1.91	1	High
4. Group work activities create conflict and collision in each student.	10	16	42	29	12	3.16	1.78	2	Moderately High
5. Group work activities bring an intense environment in the classroom.	9	16	42	34	8	3.15	1.77	3	Moderately High
6. Group work activities create arguments and miscommunication.	12	18	43	23	13	2.94	1.71	7	Moderately High
7. Group work activities are hard to manage	12	22	40	22	13	3.02	1.74	6	Moderately High

because of my classmates.									
8. Group work activities have many ideas and thoughts, which made me confuse.	11	19	41	29	9	3.06	1.75	5	Moderately High
9. Group work activities cannot build lifelong learning.	15	42	30	15	7	2.61	1.61	9	Moderately High
10. Groupwork activities do not develop my emotion and thoughts in the study.	20	37	30	18	4	2.53	1.59	10	Low
Average Weighted Mean						2.99	1.73		Moderately High

Table 4 shows that senior high school students chose group work activities some of the students just relied upon their classmates' efforts. Therefore, some of the students develop a dependency on their classmates without initiative in the classroom (Chiriac et al., 2011; Mittlemeier, 2018; & Seric, 2018). While some of the students had a conflict and collisions in the class activities in the lesson, the students had a conflict of ideas and thoughts in distributing the lesson. Then, most of the students experience an intense environment in the classroom due to the conflict of the lesson (Fabian et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The data showed that the students preferred group activities in the discussion, reporting, and role-playing during the class lesson. These indicated that discussion prepared to share ideas in the classroom in which students construct knowledge. Moreover, that discussion builds group work activities in which communication is essential in-class engagement. While in reporting, the students search for information and students present in the classroom. Students interact with their classmates to know the parts of reporting in the presentation. Then role-playing is an activity that involves imitating and copying the characters of the story or scenario in the lesson. Some students enjoyed role-playing in a light environment by wearing costumes and exchanging the acts.

The students chose group work activities because of engagement in the classroom. Each student participates in the classroom because of group work activities. As well as developing their communication, students enhance communication in class. The senior high school students said group work activities help them to learn faster.

However, students also believed that group work activities lead some students to rely upon their classmates' efforts. Students relied on the work of their classmates in the classroom. At the same time, it creates conflict and collision in the group. Moreover, it brought an intense environment in the classroom.

Recommendations

The research showed the importance of group work activities in senior high school students in terms of socialization and learning. Despite of advantages of group work activities, there still are disadvantages of group activities for the students. According to the responses of the participants in the group work activities, some students rely upon the efforts of their classmates. Therefore, the researchers suggest that the teachers, school staff, and school administrators design self-regulatory activities and programs that fit the learners' engagement. Let the students become more participative in the class by encouraging and informing the benefits of the activities. Moreover, the teacher layouts his activities that encourage the learners to cooperate in the class with their classmates, which balances the punishments and rewards in the class. The classroom has an environment of fun and enjoyment so that students participate in the lesson. The school administration discussed the implementation of group work activities in the classroom so that students will be involved in the classroom. The school will conduct extended research on learning development in conducting group-work activities.

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